

EXTENDED MATERIALS AND METHODS

UCE sequencing and processing

For the newly sequenced species, we extracted genomic DNA with the DNeasy blood and tissue kit (Qiagen, Germantown, MD, USA) and submitted samples to Arbor Biosciences (Ann Arbor, MI, USA) for library enrichment with the *Acanthomorpha* 1Kv1 probe set targeting 1,314 UCE loci (Alfaro et al. 2018) and Illumina sequencing. We trimmed adapters and cleaned raw Illumina reads for newly sequenced species with *Trimmomatic* (Bolger et al. 2014), combined new data with published assemblies from UCE target-enriched and whole genome sequencing, and assembled reads for each species with ABySS (Simpson et al. 2009) using the PhyIUCE v1.7.3 pipeline (Faircloth 2016). We then extracted UCE sequences from assemblies, aligned individual loci, and generated a 75% complete matrix with PhyIUCE v1.7.3 (Faircloth 2016) that consisted of 147 UCE loci and 117,081 base pairs. Our matrix contained 270 species including 265 *Gobiiformes* and 5 outgroups representing *Beryciformes*, *Ophidiiformes*, *Batrachoididae*, and *Scombriformes*.

Phylogenetic analysis and calibration

We used IQ-TREE2 2.3.6 to infer maximum likelihood (ML) phylogeny for the 75% complete dataset, using both the unpartitioned matrix and a partition scheme inferred by Partition Finder 2.1.1 (Nguyen et al. 2015; Lanfear et al. 2017; Minh et al. 2020), and assessing nodal support with 1,000 ultrafast bootstrap replicates. To evaluate areas of discordance between the species and gene trees, we inferred relationships for the individual UCE locus alignments under the multispecies coalescent model, constructed a gene tree with ASTRAL-III 5.7.8, and

visualized branch support with local posterior probabilities (Zhang et al. 2018). We then used IQ-TREE2 to calculate gene concordance factors (gCF) and site concordance factors (sCF), in order to identify branches of the topology that showed discordance among inferred gene, site, and species histories (Minh et al. 2020; Lanfear and Hahn 2024).

Partitioned and unpartitioned ML analyses yielded the same topology, so for computational efficiency we used the unpartitioned dataset for time calibration with BEAST 2.7.7 (Bouckaert et al. 2014, 2019). We assigned nine fossils to nodes in the phylogeny as lognormal priors, with the midpoint of the fossil age range used as the mean and the standard deviation selected such that 95% of the age distribution encompasses the fossil age interval:

1. †*Leptolumamia vetula*: mean 48.5 Ma, standard deviation 0.01, placed at the most recent common ancestor (MRCA) of *Apogoninae* and *Amioidinae* (Bannikov and Fraser 2016).
2. †*Oligopseudamia iancurtisi*: mean 30 Ma, standard deviation 0.07, placed at the MRCA of *Pseudaminae* (Marramá et al. 2022).
3. †*Paralates chapelcornerensis*: mean 36.0 Ma, standard deviation 0.03, placed at the MRCA of *Rhyacichthyidae* and *Odontobutidae* (Gierl and Reichenbacher 2017).
4. †*Eleogobius gaudanti*: mean 17.0 Ma, standard deviation 0.03, placed at the MRCA of *Thalasseleotrididae* (Gierl and Reichenbacher 2015; Gierl et al. 2022; Dirnberger et al. 2024).
5. †*Lepidocottus aries*: mean 23.5 Ma, standard deviation 0.03, placed at the MRCA of *Butidae* (Gierl et al. 2013; Gierl et al. 2022).
6. †*Mataichthys bictenatus*: mean 17.5 Ma, standard deviation 0.045, placed at the MRCA of *Gobiomorphus* and *Philypnodon* (Schwarzahns et al. 2011).

7. †*Simpsonigobius nerimanae*: mean 18.3 Ma, standard deviation 0.04, placed at the MRCA of the *Acanthogobius* and *Mugilogobius* lineages (Dirnberger et al. 2024).
8. †*Oniketia akimotoi*: mean 30 Ma, standard deviation 0.07, placed at the MRCA of *Gobiidae* (Marramá et al. 2022; Reichenbacher et al. 2025).
9. †*Gobius jarosi*: mean 19.1 Ma, standard deviation 0.01, placed at the MRCA of *Gobius niger* and *G. ophiocephalus* (Reichenbacher et al. 2018; Gierl et al. 2022).

The placements of the fossils on the tree are shown in Supplementary Figure S7. We also used a lognormal prior centered at 100 Ma at the root of *Gobiiformes*, in accordance with stem ages of *Gobiiformes* inferred in other studies based on UCE data (Alfaro et al. 2018; Ghezelayagh et al. 2022). For computational efficiency, we ran the calibration analysis on three nonoverlapping subsets of 10 UCE loci and combined the results. Using the MultiMonophyleticConstraint prior in BEAUti 2 (Bouckaert et al. 2014), we constrained the tree topology to that derived from the ML analysis and prevented alterations to the topology by setting the Bactrian Subtree Slide, Narrow Exchange, Wide Exchange, and Wilson Balding operators to zero. We ran the analyses for 250-300 million MCMC generations (until convergence was achieved), removed the first 10% of trees as burnin, and examined the trace and ESS values with Tracer v1.7 to confirm confirmed that expected sample size (ESS) values for the prior, posterior, and tree likelihoods exceeded 200 (Rambaut et al. 2018). We then combined the trees for the three 10-locus UCE runs with LogCombiner 2.7.7 and constructed a majority rule consensus tree using TreeAnnotator 2.7.7 (Bouckaert et al. 2014, 2019). Finally, we repeated the BEAST calibration analysis with sampling only from the prior (disregarding the alignment) and confirmed that the posterior age estimates were shifted relative to those inferred from the priors.

Diversification analyses

To examine diversification patterns within *Gobioidei*, we analyzed the tree of 229 species using both BAMM and TESS-CoMET. Due to the uneven sampling within gobioid lineages, we corrected sampling fraction in each family and lineage individually for analysis of diversification dynamics with BAMM 2.5.0 (Rabosky 2014). We set input priors for the calibrated phylogeny using the R package *BAMMtools* 2.1.10 (Rabosky et al. 2014), ran the MCMC chain for ten million generations, and used *BAMMtools* to check ESS values and ensure convergence. We performed TESS-CoMET analyses using the R package *TESS* 2.1.2 (Höhna et al. 2016; May et al. 2016), including a single correction for sampling fraction across the phylogeny of 0.093. We set the speciation prior at 0.10, the extinction rate prior to 0.02 and the survival probability to 0.50 based on the estimates of goby faunal turnover given in Schwarzhans et al. (2020), ran one million MCMC generations and discarded 10% of replicates as burnin. We then repeated the analysis using hyperpriors inferred by TESS-CoMET, and again with the probability of mass extinctions set to zero.

Although our analysis included the most complete taxon set for *Gobiiformes* yet assembled, we sampled only 9.3% of the total species diversity. To evaluate the robustness of our diversification results given our incomplete sampling, we used our phylogenomic hypothesis as a backbone for stochastically resolving all species of *Gobioidei* using TACT (Rabosky et al. 2018; Chang et al. 2020) guided by the taxonomic groups identified in previous studies (Agorreta et al. 2013; Thacker 2015; McCraney et al. 2020). We generated 100 fully sampled trees for *Gobioidei* and repeated the BAMM and TESS analyses on each tree. Another potential concern is that the inferred speciation and extinction rates are imprecise due to non-identifiability, meaning that infinite combinations of speciation and extinction rates (the congruence class) can yield the same

net diversification patterns on any given phylogeny (Louca and Pennell 2020; Kopperud et al. 2023). To explore this possibility, we used the R package *CRABS* (Helmstetter et al. 2022; Höhna et al. 2022) to infer pulled diversification rates for both the BAMM and TESS results. We compared evolutionary trajectories across a range of constant extinction rates, linearly increasing extinction rates, exponentially increasing extinction rates, and scenarios in which extinction rates varied in opposition to the speciation rates, to determine whether the diversification rate shifts identified in the BAMM and TESS analyses were sensitive to variations across their congruence classes. R code used to perform these analyses, input files, and full output for the BAMM, TESS, and CRABS analyses are available in the Dryad repository (<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.c59zw3rq8>).

Trait-dependent diversification analyses

Using BiSSE, MuSSE, and HiSSE, we compared trait evolution models in which speciation and extinction rates were constrained to be equal or allowed to vary, using 10,000 MCMC generations sampled every 100 generations. After removing 10% of the replicates as burnin, we visually checked for convergence of posteriors in the run trace and plotted histograms for speciation, extinction, and net diversification rates associated with each character state. To assess the potential contribution of hidden states to the diversification rate estimates, we repeated all BiSSE and MuSSE analyses using HiSSE, comparing four models of diversification rate variation with model fit assessed using Akaike information criterion (AIC) scores: a null model in which turnover and extinction fraction did not differ between character states, a BiSSE model in which turnover and extinction fraction varied across character states but hidden states were not present, a character-dependent (CD) HiSSE model in which turnover and extinction fraction

could vary across all states, and a character-independent (CID) HiSSE model in which turnover and extinction fraction could vary only across the hidden states. We visualized the distribution of states on the phylogenetic tree for each phenotypic or ecological character by performing ancestral state reconstruction with 1,000 replications of stochastic character mapping simulation for each trait using the R package *phytools* 2.3-0 (Revell 2024). We were not able to evaluate the potential effect of incomplete taxon sampling on the SSE analyses as we did with the diversification analyses because the stochastic resolution of our TACT trees introduces uncertainty in the reconstruction of trait distributions that distorts the underlying phylogenetic signal and can bias the evolutionary rate estimates (Rabosky 2015).

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